

Synthesis and microbial activity of pyrazolines

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Abstract : Claisen-Schmidt reaction of different aromatic aldehydes with acetone gave α,β -unsaturated ketones (1a-7a) which on further reaction with hydrazine hydrate in the presence of glacial acetic acid afforded pyrazolines (1b-7b). Synthesized compounds were characterized by their IR, ¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR spectra. All the synthesized pyrazolines were screened for their microbial activity against *Bacillus* sp., *Pseudomonas* sp., *Acinetobacter* sp. and *Klebsiella* sp. Pyrazolines having substitution on benzene ring exhibited lower MIC values than pyrazolines having no substitution on benzene ring for all the tested bacteria. All pyrazolines exhibited less activity than standard ampicillin at all concentrations. Some of the synthesized compounds showed promising to moderate activity against all the microbes.

Keywords : α,β -Unsaturated ketones, pyrazolines, minimum inhibitory concentration.

Introduction

Heterocycles form the largest classical division of organic chemistry. Pyrazolines are one of the most important classes of heterocyclic compounds having their broad spectrum of application in agrochemical and pharmaceutical field. The term pyrazole was given to this class of compounds by Ludwig Knorr in 1883. The first natural pyrazole; 1-pyrazolyl alanine was isolated from the seeds of watermelon¹.

Pyrazolines are used as antitumour², immunosuppressive³, antibacterial⁴ and antitubercular agents. Some of the pyrazoline derivatives are reported to possess anti-inflammatory⁵, anticancer⁶, antidiabetic⁷ and antidepressant properties⁸. Pyrazoline derivatives also find applications as dyestuffs and analytical reagents⁹.

Keeping in view the potential biological activity of pyrazolines, it was perceived that the synergistic effect of heterocyclic moieties in single nucleus might result in the formation of some worth-while molecules. Therefore the present investigation was carried out for the synthesis and microbial activity of different pyrazolines.

Results and discussion

Desired pyrazolines were synthesized according to steps depicted in Fig. 1. Chalcones (α,β -unsaturated ketones) were taken as starting materials which were synthesized by using Claisen-Schmidt reaction. Different aromatic aldehydes were reacted with acetone in presence of sodium hydroxide (10%). Equal moles of both the reactants were taken to avoid formation of dibenzalacetone. As ketones are less reactive towards nucleophilic addition, probability of formation of self-condensation product of acetone can be ignored. Physical data (yield, melting point, *R_f*, state and colour) of chalcones were determined (Table 1). Pyrazolines were synthesized from chalcones in ethanolic medium in presence of few drops of glacial acetic acid. All compounds were characterized by their spectral data (IR, ¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR).

IR data :

IR spectral data revealed the formation of pyrazolines from chalcones. Broad stretching band in range of 3424–3254 cm⁻¹ was due to N-H of pyrazoline ring. N-N, C=N and C-N stretching were also observed in range of 1527–1514 cm⁻¹, 1606–1590 cm⁻¹ and 1378–1348 cm⁻¹ res-

Fig. 1

Table 1. Physical parameters of α,β -unsaturated ketones

Compd.	Colour	Yield (%)	R _f	Melting point (°C)
1a	Orange yellow	78	0.61	42–43
2a	Light brown	88	0.59	120–122
3a	Yellow	83	0.58	97–99
4a	Yellow	95	0.56	63–65
5a	Yellow	94	0.54	72–73
6a	Pale yellow	72	0.55	94–95
7a	Yellow	84	0.54	128–130

All α,β -unsaturated ketones were obtained in solid form.

pectively which further assured the formation of five membered pyrazoline ring. The presence of C=C in aromatic ring was confirmed due to visibility of band at 1474–1431 cm⁻¹. Band for O-H stretching was observed for compounds **6b** and **7b** having hydroxy group on aromatic ring.

¹H NMR data :

The formation of desired pyrazolines was confirmed from data presented by ¹H NMR spectrum. A singlet

corresponding to N-H of pyrazoline ring appeared in range of δ 7.72–7.88. The two hydrogens on C-4 of pyrazoline ring (Fig. 2) were not found equivalent. Double doublets were obtained for both of these protons in the range of δ 2.51–2.65 (*J* 18.1–18.4, 4.1–4.5 Hz) and δ 3.22–3.41 (*J* 18.3–18.5, 11.2–11.7 Hz). Proton at C-5 of pyrazoline also appeared as double doublet between δ 4.16–4.32 (*J* 11.3–11.7, 4.2–4.7 Hz) for pyrazolines. Aromatic protons appeared as multiplet in range of δ 6.50–7.71. More confirmation to the formation of pyrazolines provided by coupling constant values of double doublets.

¹³C NMR data :

Further assurance to the formation of desired compounds was added by ¹³C NMR data. Out of three carbons of pyrazoline ring, C-3 of pyrazoline ring (Fig. 2) in contact with electronegative nitrogen atom corresponding to C=N showed a maximum downfield shift δ 153.83 in the spectrum of compound **1b**. C-4 and C-5 of pyrazoline ring appeared near δ 45.59 and δ 51.13 respectively. The ¹³C NMR spectra of compounds **4b**, **5b** and **7b** showed peak in the range of δ 52.81–57.34 indicating the presence of methoxy (OCH₃) group on benzene ring.

Fig. 2

Microbial activity :

Bacillus sp. :

The data presented in the Table 2 exhibited that all the compounds were active against *Bacillus* sp. at 250 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ concentration with inhibition zone in range of 9.0–10.5 mm. At 500 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, compound **2b** having chloro group at *ortho* position of benzene ring showed inhibition zone of 12.0 mm which was significantly higher than other tested compounds. Compound **5b** having methoxy group at *meta* position showed same activity as compound **1b** at this concentration. At higher concentrations (1000 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and 3000 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) compound **2b** with *ortho* chloro group was found to be more active than other compounds except standard.

Table 2. Microbial activity of different pyrazolines on the growth of *Bacillus* sp.

Compd.	Diameter of growth inhibition zone (mm)				
	3000 ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	2000 ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	1000 ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	500 ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	250 ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)
1b	12.0	12.0	11.5	10.5	10.5
2b	13.0	12.0	12.0	12.0	10.5
3b	12.0	12.0	11.5	11.0	10.0
4b	11.5	10.5	10.5	10.0	9.0
5b	12.0	11.5	11.0	10.5	10.0
6b	12.0	12.0	11.5	11.0	10.0
7b	11.0	10.5	10.0	9.5	9.0
Ampicillin	28.0	27.0	18.5	17.5	15.5
CD ($p = 0.05$)	0.62	0.42	0.34	0.44	0.54

All pyrazolines were further studied for minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) values (Fig. 3). Compound **1b** was having maximum MIC value (240 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) with no substitution on benzene ring. Compounds having methoxy group at *meta* position (**5b**) and hydroxy group at *para* position (**6b**) exhibited lowest minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) value (170 $\mu\text{g/ml}$). Pyrazoline having

Fig. 3. Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) of different pyrazolines against *Bacillus* sp.

both hydroxy and methoxy group on benzene ring showed comparable minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) value (180 $\mu\text{g/ml}$). Pyrazolines with chloro group at *ortho* and *para* positions of benzene ring registered minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) values of 180 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and 190 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ respectively. All the pyrazolines having substitution on benzene ring exhibited lower MIC values than pyrazolines having no substitution on benzene ring.

Pseudomonas sp. :

Results of screening of different pyrazolines against

Pseudomonas sp. are presented in Table 3. Compound **5b** having methoxy group at *meta* position of benzene ring exhibited significantly higher activity than all other compounds with an inhibition zone of 10.0 mm at 250 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. No activity was shown by compounds **1b** (no substitution on benzene ring) and **6b** (hydroxy group *para* position of benzene ring) at 250 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. Presence of chloro group at *ortho* position (compound **2b**) and methoxy group at *meta* position of benzene ring (compound **5b**) exhibited significantly higher activity at 500 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ with an inhibition zone of 10.5 mm. Compound **2b** and **4b** exhibited similar activity at 2000 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and 3000 $\mu\text{g/ml}$.

Table 3. Microbial activity of different pyrazolines on the growth of *Pseudomonas* sp.

Compd.	Diameter of growth inhibition zone (mm)				
	3000 ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	2000 ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	1000 ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	500 ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	250 ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)
1b	12.5	12.0	11.5	10.0	0
2b	11.0	11.0	10.5	10.5	9.5
3b	10.0	9.5	9.0	9.0	9.0
4b	11.0	11.0	10.0	9.5	9.0
5b	12.5	12.0	11.0	10.5	10.0
6b	10.0	9.5	8.5	8.0	0
7b	10.0	9.0	9.0	9.0	8.5
Ampicillin	24.0	20.0	18.0	16.5	15.0
CD ($p = 0.05$)	0.17	0.17	0.17	0.17	0.17

All pyrazolines were significantly less active than standard ampicillin at all concentrations. All the compounds showed significant differences among themselves at all the concentrations.

Minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) values of different pyrazolines against *Pseudomonas* sp. are presented in Fig. 4. Data in graph revealed that all the substituted pyrazolines irrespective of groups exhibited lower MIC value as compared to unsubstituted pyrazolines. Benzene ring having substitution of *ortho* chloro group and *para* chloro group (**2b** and **3b**) exhibited lowest MIC value of 170 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and 150 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ respectively. Presence of both hydroxy and methoxy group on benzene ring in compound **7b** lowered the MIC to 160 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. All the pyrazolines having substitution on benzene ring exhibited lower MIC values than pyrazolines having no substitution on benzene ring.

Fig. 4. Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) of different pyrazolines against *Pseudomonas* sp.

Acinetobacter sp. :

Results of microbial screening of different pyrazolines against *Acinetobacter* sp. (Table 4) exhibited that none of the compounds except compound **3b** (having *para* chloro group on benzene ring) and **7b** (having methoxy and hydroxy group on benzene ring) were active at 250 µg/ml. Compound **2b** having *ortho* chloro group on benzene ring was found to show significantly higher activity than all other compounds at 500, 1000, 2000 and 3000 µg/ml with inhibition zone of 11.5, 12.5, 14.0 and 15.5 mm respectively. Pyrazoline with *ortho* methoxy group on benzene ring (compound **4b**) exhibited inhibition zone of 14.0 mm at 3000 µg/ml. Activity of all pyrazolines was found to be significantly lower than standard ampicillin at all the tested concentrations. All the compounds showed significant differences among themselves at all the concentrations.

Table 4. Microbial activity of different pyrazolines on the growth of *Acinetobacter* sp.

Compd.	Diameter of growth inhibition zone (mm)				
	3000 (µg/ml)	2000 (µg/ml)	1000 (µg/ml)	500 (µg/ml)	250 (µg/ml)
1b	13.0	13.0	12.0	0	0
2b	15.5	14.0	12.5	11.5	0
3b	13.0	12.5	11.5	10.0	9
4b	14.0	11.5	10.0	9.5	0
5b	12.0	12.0	11.0	10.5	0
6b	12.0	11.5	10.5	9.0	0
7b	11.5	11.0	9.5	8.0	8.0
Ampicillin	25.0	23.0	17.0	16.5	15.0
CD (<i>p</i> = 0.05)	0.17	0.17	0.17	0.17	0.17

Minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) values of different pyrazolines against *Acinetobacter* sp. are presented in Fig. 5. Compound **1b** (no substitution on benzene ring) was having maximum MIC value of 700 µg/ml. Compounds having *para* chloro group (**3b**) and both hydroxy and methoxy group (**7b**) exhibited lowest minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) value (230 µg/ml). Presence of methoxy group at *ortho* and *meta* position (compound **4b** and **5b**) lowered the MIC value to 400 µg/ml and 450 µg/ml respectively. Compound **6b** having hydroxy group at *para* position of benzene ring exhibited MIC value of 300 µg/ml. All the pyrazolines having substitution on benzene ring exhibited lower MIC values than pyrazolines having no substitution on benzene ring.

Fig. 5. Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) of different pyrazolines against *Acinetobacter* sp.

Klebsiella sp. :

Data given in Table 5 showed that all other compounds were active against *Klebsiella* sp. at 250 µg/ml except compound **1b** (no substitution on benzene ring) and com-

Table 5. Microbial activity of different pyrazolines on the growth of *Klebsiella* sp.

Compd.	Diameter of growth inhibition zone (mm)				
	3000 (µg/ml)	2000 (µg/ml)	1000 (µg/ml)	500 (µg/ml)	250 (µg/ml)
1b	12.5	12.0	12.0	11.5	0
2b	14.0	13.5	12.5	12.5	0
3b	13.0	11.5	11.5	10.5	10.0
4b	16.5	15.0	14.5	13.5	12.0
5b	12.5	12.0	11.5	10.5	9.0
6b	15.0	12.5	12.5	12.0	10.5
7b	14.0	13.0	13.0	11.5	11.0
Ampicillin	30.0	23.0	17.0	16.5	15.0
CD (<i>p</i> = 0.05)	0.17	0.17	0.17	0.17	0.17

pound **2b** (*ortho* chloro group at benzene ring). Pyrazoline (**4b**) with methoxy group at *ortho* position of benzene ring exhibited highest activity at all tested concentrations with inhibition zone in range of 12.0–16.5 mm. Compound **6b** having *para* hydroxy group on benzene ring was also found to show good inhibitory effect against *Klebsiella* sp. at 3000 µg/ml with inhibition zone of 15.0 mm. Compound **2b** exhibited inhibition effect with zones of 14.0, 13.5 and 12.5 mm at 3000, 2000 and 1000 µg/ml respectively. However activity of all tested pyrazolines was found to be significantly lower than standard ampicillin. All the compounds showed significant differences among themselves at all the concentrations.

Minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) data of pyrazolines against *Klebsiella* sp. (Fig. 6) showed that compound **1b** with no substitution on benzene ring exhibited highest MIC value of 550 µg/ml. All other pyrazolines were active against tested organism at concentrations lower than this value. Compound **7b** having both methoxy and hydroxy group exhibited lowest MIC values of 150 µg/ml followed by compound **4b** having *ortho* methoxy group on benzene ring. Compounds **3b** (having *para* chloro group) and **6b** (having *para* hydroxy group) registered same minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) value (190 µg/ml).

Fig. 6. Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) of different pyrazolines against *Klebsiella* sp.

Experimental

General :

All the recorded melting points were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected. Structures of compounds were confirmed by routine spectrometric analysis. IR, ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra were scanned from

Sophisticated Analytical Instrumentation Facility (SAIF), Central Instrument Laboratory (CIL), Panjab University, Chandigarh. The IR spectra of compounds were recorded using KBr discs on Perkin-Elmer FTIR spectrophotometer. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker Avance II 400 MHz and ¹³C NMR were recorded on a Bruker Avance II 100 MHz instrument using TMS as an internal standard.

General method for synthesis of α,β -unsaturated ketones (**1a-7a**) :

Equal moles (0.01) of differently substituted benzaldehydes and acetone were dissolved in ethanol in a 250 ml flask placed on a magnetic stirrer. 2–3 drops of sodium hydroxide (10%) were added to this mixture slowly, while temperature was maintained between 25–30 °C. The mixture was stirred at room temperature for 2 h. It was then made acidic by the addition of 2 N hydrochloric acid and transferred to a separatory funnel. Benzene (20 ml) was added to it. The upper organic layer was removed, lower aqueous layer was again extracted with 20 ml of benzene. The combined organic layers were then dried with anhydrous sodium sulphate. Benzene was removed by distillation on a water bath. Crude solid obtained was recrystallized from petroleum ether : ethyl acetate (7 : 3).

General method for synthesis of pyrazolines (**1b-7b**) :

Equal moles (0.01) of α,β -unsaturated ketones (**1a-7a**) and hydrazine hydrate were taken in ethanol (20 ml) in a round bottom flask. Acetic acid (catalytic amount) was added to it and refluxed for 8 h. The progress of reaction was monitored by thin layer chromatography (TLC) from time to time. After completion of reaction, the contents were kept at room temperature and then poured into ice cold water. The solid obtained was filtered and washed with cold water. The pure product was obtained after recrystallization from ethanol.

Microbial activity :

The effect of pyrazolines on the growth of *Bacillus* sp., *Pseudomonas* sp., *Acinetobacter* sp. and *Klebsiella* sp. was assessed by bacterial sensitivity – filter paper disc method. The plates were prepared by pouring 15–20 ml of the sterilized nutrient agar media (*Bacillus* sp., *Acinetobacter* sp. and *Klebsiella* sp.) and King's B (*Pseudomonas* sp.) on sterilized petriplates. Plates were

then allowed to solidify and stored for 2 days to ensure sterility. Suspension of 3–4 days old broth of the test organism (*Bacillus* sp., *Pseudomonas* sp., *Acinetobacter* sp. and *Klebsiella* sp.) was then spread on the required medium plates. Stock solution of test compounds (3000 µg/ml) was prepared in dimethyl sulphoxide and stored at 4 °C for further use. The stock solution was diluted to 2000, 1000, 500 and 250 µg/ml. Sterile filter paper discs moistened with test compound solution in dimethyl sulphoxide (DMSO) were carefully placed on the medium under aseptic conditions inoculated with the respective bacterial suspension. Sterilized filter paper discs dipped in dimethyl sulphoxide served as control. Plates were incubated at 28 ± 1 °C and the diameter of growth inhibition zone (mm) was measured after 24 h. The growth of the organism on medium containing the test compound was also compared with the growth on the plates containing micro-organism without test compound as control.

3-Methyl-5-phenyl-4,5-dihydro-1H-pyrazole (1b) : Yield 65%; m.p. 129–131 °C; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 3424 (N-H str.), 3027 (aromatic C-H str.), 2925 (ν_{as} CH_2), 1595 (C=N str.), 1536 (N-N str.), 1453 (C=C str.), 1374 (C-N str.), 864 (C-N bending), 756 (N-H bending) and 700 cm^{-1} (C=C bending); ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3 , δ , ppm) : 2.05 (3H, s, CH_3), 2.57–2.64 (1H, dd, CH_2) (J 18.3, 4.3 Hz), 3.33–3.40 (1H, dd, CH_2) (J 18.5, 11.4 Hz), 4.22–4.26 (1H, dd, CH) (J 11.6, 4.4 Hz), 7.39–7.59 (5H, m, Ar-H), 7.75 (1H, s, NH); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3 , δ , ppm) : 18.58 (CH_3), 45.59 (CH_2), 51.13 (CH), 153.83 (C=N), 112.62–145.33 (aromatic carbons).

5-(2-Chlorophenyl)-3-methyl-4,5-dihydro-1H-pyrazole (2b) : Yield 72%; m.p. 128–130 °C; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 3327 (N-H str.), 3059 (aromatic C-H str.), 2927 (ν_{as} CH_2), 1590 (C=N str.), 1535 (N-N str.), 1473 (C=C str.), 1378 (C-N str.), 1036 (C-Cl str.), 869 (C-N bending), 828 (C-H bending), 752 (N-H bending) and 694 cm^{-1} (C=C bending); ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3 , δ , ppm) : 2.08 (3H, s, CH_3), 2.55–2.62 (1H, dd, CH_2) (J 18.1, 4.3 Hz), 3.35–3.41 (1H, dd, CH_2) (J 18.4, 11.3 Hz), 4.22–4.25 (1H, dd, CH) (J 11.5, 4.4 Hz), 7.41–7.65 (4H, m, Ar-H), 7.72 (1H, s, NH); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3 , δ , ppm) : 16.32 (CH_3), 45.52 (CH_2), 49.22 (CH), 152.82 (C=N), 121.11–146.32 (aromatic carbons).

5-(4-Chlorophenyl)-3-methyl-4,5-dihydro-1H-pyrazole (3b) : Yield 70%; m.p. 145–146 °C; IR (KBr cm^{-1}) : 3325 (N-H str.), 3055 (aromatic C-H str.), 2925 (ν_{as} CH_2), 1595 (C=N str.), 1535 (N-N str.), 1474 (C=C str.), 1372 (C-N str.), 1039 (C-Cl str.), 869 (C-N bending), 830 (C-H bending), 759 (N-H bending) and 695 cm^{-1} (C=C bending); ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3 , δ , ppm) : 2.05 (3H, s, CH_3), 2.56–2.65 (1H, dd, CH_2) (J 18.2, 4.2 Hz), 3.29–3.37 (1H, dd, CH_2) (J 18.5, 11.2 Hz), 4.21–4.25 (1H, dd, CH) (J 11.4, 4.2 Hz), 7.39–7.58 (4H, m, Ar-H), 7.78 (1H, s, NH); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3 , δ , ppm) : 20.29 (CH_3), 47.53 (CH_2), 49.28 (CH), 157.88 (C=N), 111.89–145.43 (aromatic carbons).

5-(2-Methoxyphenyl)-3-methyl-4,5-dihydro-1H-pyrazole (4b) : Yield 85%; m.p. 127–129 °C; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 3416 (N-H str.), 2989 (aromatic C-H str.), 2929 (ν_{as} CH_2), 1598 (C=N str.), 1530 (N-N str.), 1458 (C=C str.), 1374 (C-N str.), 1149 (ν_{as} C-O str.), 1043 (ν_{s} C-O str.), 869 (C-N bending), 828 (C-H bending), 783 (N-H bending) and 698 cm^{-1} (C=C bending); ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) : 2.01 (3H, s, CH_3), 3.11 (3H, s, OCH_3), 2.54–2.62 (1H, dd, CH_2) (J 18.3, 4.1 Hz), 3.37–3.45 (1H, dd, CH_2) (J 18.3, 11.6 Hz), 4.19–4.24 (1H, dd, CH) (J 11.7, 4.7 Hz), 7.30–7.56 (4H, m, Ar-H), 7.75 (1H, s, NH); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3 , δ , ppm) : 19.39 (CH_3), 49.82 (CH_2), 51.13 (CH), 156.44 (C=N), 57.39 (OCH_3), 115.46–153.21 (aromatic carbons).

5-(3-Methoxyphenyl)-3-methyl-4,5-dihydro-1H-pyrazole (5b) : Yield 83%; m.p. 131–133 °C; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 3412 (N-H str.), 2999 (aromatic C-H str.), 2935 (ν_{as} CH_2), 1600 (C=N str.), 1530 (N-N str.), 1453 (C=C str.), 1371 (C-N str.), 1155 (ν_{as} C-O str.), 1048 (ν_{s} C-O str.), 869 (C-N bending), 832 (C-H bending), 781 (N-H bending) and 699 cm^{-1} (C=C bending); ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3 , δ , ppm) : 2.06 (3H, s, CH_3), 3.66 (3H, s, OCH_3), 2.52–2.61 (1H, dd, CH_2) (J 18.3, 4.5 Hz), 3.30–3.40 (1H, dd, CH_2) (J 18.4, 11.7 Hz), 4.16–4.21 (1H, dd, CH) (J 11.3, 4.2 Hz), 7.32–7.59 (4H, m, Ar-H), 7.80 (1H, s, NH); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3 , δ , ppm) : 18.55 (CH_3), 45.73 (CH_2), 51.13 (CH), 154.38 (C=N), 58.12 (OCH_3), 112.83–152.44 (aromatic carbons).

5-(4-Hydroxyphenyl)-3-methyl-4,5-dihydro-1H-pyrazole (6b) : Yield 60%; m.p. 209–211 °C; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 3425 (O-H str.), 3253 (N-H str.), 3077 (aromatic C-H

str.), 2974 (ν_{as} CH₂), 1606 (C=N str.), 1514 (N-N str.), 1431 (C=C str.), 1348 (C-N str.), 1170 (ν_{as} C-O str.), 1021 (ν_{s} C-O str.), 842 (C-N bending), 832 (C-H bending), 796 (N-H bending) and 695 cm⁻¹ (C=C bending); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆, δ , ppm) : 2.02 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.51–2.64 (1H, dd, CH₂) (*J* 18.4, 4.2 Hz), 3.22–3.29 (1H, dd, CH₂) (*J* 18.5, 11.2 Hz), 4.28–4.32 (1H, dd, CH) (*J* 11.7, 4.3 Hz), 7.44–7.69 (4H, m, Ar-H), 7.82 (1H, s, NH), 8.71 (1H, s, OH); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆, δ , ppm) : 15.33 (CH₃), 47.22 (CH₂), 49.73 (CH), 157.56 (C=N), 114.43–149.64 (aromatic carbons).

2-Methoxy-4-(3-methyl-4,5-dihydro-1H-pyrazol-5-yl)phenol (7b) : Yield 54%; m.p. 185–186 °C; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 3412 (O-H str.), 3253 (N-H str.), 2974 (aromatic C-H str.), 2850 (ν_{as} CH₂), 1606 (C=N str.), 1514 (N-N str.), 1431 (C=C str.), 1393 (C-N str.), 1127 (ν_{as} C-O str.), 1021 (ν_{s} C-O str.), 848 (C-N bending), 796 (N-H bending) and 695 cm⁻¹ (C=C bending); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆, δ , ppm) : 2.20 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.72 (3H, s, OCH₃), 2.53–2.55 (1H, dd, CH₂) (*J* 18.3, 4.3 Hz), 3.32–3.40 (1H, dd, CH₂) (*J* 18.5, 11.4 Hz), 4.22–4.26 (1H, dd, CH) (*J* 11.6, 4.4 Hz), 7.44–7.51 (3H, m, Ar-H), 7.88 (1H, s, NH), 9.69 (1H, s, OH); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆, δ , ppm) : 20.09 (CH₃), 46.22 (CH₂), 46.44 (CH), 158.91 (C=N), 55.85 (OCH₃), 125.08–146.25 (aromatic carbons).

Conclusion

Different aldehydes were treated with acetone in the presence of sodium hydroxide to yield α,β -unsaturated ketones (**1a-7a**) which on treatment with hydrazine hy-

drate gave pyrazolines (**1b-7b**). Synthesized compounds were screened for their microbial activity against *Bacillus* sp., *Pseudomonas* sp., *Acinetobactor* sp. and *Klebsiella* sp. All the pyrazolines having substitution on benzene ring exhibited lower MIC values than pyrazolines having no substitution on benzene ring for all tested bacteria. All pyrazolines exhibited less activity than standard ampicillin at all the tested concentrations.

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